

**PROBLEMS OF DEVELOPING THE SOCIAL COMPETENCE OF STUDENTS
IN THE PROCESS OF HIGHER PEDAGOGICAL EDUCATION**

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Abstract

In the article, the didactic support of the educational process based on professional characteristics as well as the qualification requirements of students in the development of social competence, the tasks of choosing individual approaches in the implementation of the educational process with the problems of social competence development, conclusions and recommendations are presented.

Keywords: social competence, individual regulation, creative activity, social professional value, social culture, social knowledge, exchange of interaction, social-communication process.

In our republic, the legal-normative basis of modernizing the content of higher education, raising its quality to a higher level and involving advanced foreign experiences in this process has been improved. The tasks of "determining the priorities of the systematic reform of higher education, developing the process of training highly qualified personnel with modern knowledge and high spiritual and moral qualities, who think independently" have been defined.¹

The Government of the Republic of Uzbekistan "Introduction of mechanisms for continuous updating of professional knowledge, skills, and abilities of leaders and pedagogues, the satisfaction of professional needs of leaders and pedagogues based on scientific and pedagogical potential, integration of education, science, and production "improving the qualification requirements for the quality of the training of leaders and pedagogues by ensuring" - tasks are defined. In this regard, in the development of the professional competence of leaders and pedagogues, it is important to regularly update professional knowledge, skills, and qualifications, to improve pedagogical mechanisms and the quality of professional education based on research. This process cannot be implemented without the introduction of innovative approaches that meet world standards. Higher pedagogic education is a special object of research

in global studies as it fulfills the socio-political task of training teachers who determine the future of the whole society and the state. The more carefully social competence is formed in future teachers and the level of mobility adapted to the modern environment is developed, the more continuous education will be provided with quality personnel. This issue is gaining importance not only in national pedagogy but also on a global scale.

In the most advanced educational centers in developed countries (Center for Creative Leadership Sources, IEDP, MOOS, SPS), social competence, and creative and communicative skills are recognized as important qualities. In particular, it was determined that a modern person should have social skills and qualifications, such as creativity, social competence, communicativeness, and readiness for different ways of dealing with others (verbal, written, non-verbal). This requires improving the social competence of students in the process of higher pedagogical education, forming in them adaptability, dynamism, unique creativity and social activity, and orientation to innovative activities.

According to UNESCO's 2030 vision for international education, quality education promotes creative thinking and knowledge, and develops the fundamentals of literacy and numeracy, as well as analytical, problem-solving, reasoning, and other interpersonal and social skills at a high level. It is intended to create a comfortable educational environment that allows for acquisition. At the international level, special attention is paid to improving the quality of education, creative thinking, critical thinking, self-evaluation, and designing creative activities for students.

Nowadays, the process of globalization and intermingling of cultures is taking place all over the world. This complex process affects not only young students but also the outlook of adults. On the one hand, information technology is entering our daily lives so rapidly that we can observe it without any numbers. Currently, more than 1,500 mass media are operating in our country. These mass media contribute to the formation of information culture and ideological immunity, which are considered an important component of improving the social competence of students in the process of professional pedagogical education. Today, the problems of social education of students and ensuring their employment are common in almost all countries.

In our country, several positive things have been done to improve the social competence of students in the process of professional and pedagogical education. On the subject of youth education, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. Mirziyoyev said at the 72nd session of the UN General Assembly: "The youth of the world today are the largest generation in the history of mankind in terms of number, because they make up 2 billion people. The future and

well-being of our planet depends on how our children grow up to be human beings. Our main task is to create the necessary conditions for young people to show their potential, to prevent the spread of the "virus" of the idea of violence. For this, we believe that it is necessary to develop multilateral cooperation in social support of the young generation, protection of their rights and interests. In this regard, Uzbekistan proposes to develop a generalized international legal document - the UN International Convention on the Rights of Youth - aimed at the formation and implementation of youth policy in today's conditions of rapid development of globalization and information communication technologies. In our opinion, the countries that sign this document should undertake strict obligations to raise this area to the level of one of the main and vital priorities of their social policy" [12]. Of course, there are many positive examples in the world of improving the social competence of students, their academic and professional development activities, and the development of their creativity. Examples of these are the results achieved by young people in all types of science and technology, creativity, art, and sports. At the moment, problems are waiting to be solved in the education of young people on a global scale. Indifference to the fate and future of oneself and others, cruelty, apathy, refusal to work honestly, immorality, making a living at the expense of others, drug addiction, theft, and participation in the activities of criminal groups, extremists and terrorists It's no secret that several other destructive ideas are attracting young people to their trap. It should be noted that information technologies, including the Internet, which create conditions for learning and obtaining information, are becoming the source of several social and political problems.

1) In our country, systematic measures to eliminate the listed problems at all stages of continuous education are implemented through the tasks set at the level of state policy. The daily life of the Uzbek people, who have great ancestors such as Farghani, Bukhari, Khorezmi, Ibn Sina, Beruni, and Mirza Ulugbek, who made an invaluable scientific, cultural, and educational contribution to the Muslim and world civilization during the golden age of Islam and the Timurid renaissance. processes, including issues of education, were related to Islam. Islam, which calls for peace, creativity, science, honest work, humanity, tolerance, and nobility, was the spiritual basis of socio-economic stability and development in Central Asia until the 17th century. The age-old traditions of the Uzbek people, including traditions in the field of education, are connected with the blessing religion of our ancestors. Traditions such as greeting the elderly, respecting them, taking care of the elderly and the weak, calling for learning and learning a profession, calling for honest work, and being polite to neighbors are common in Uzbek families, their religion instilled in young people regardless of their relationship. Unfortunately, along with

young people who are forward-looking, educated, polite, and who are building their future from today, their youth, there are also unmotivated, rude, condescending, illiterate, and arrogant students. Students who live their lives in a positive spiritual, healthy, and psychologically stable environment, are open to communication, open to innovation, and show healthy views on critical thoughts, and they gain the warm relations of those around them. On the contrary, students who systematically show negative actions affect the effectiveness of education by becoming the subject of certain obstacles in any process. Therefore, this problem requires not only the tasks of education, but also the efforts of the society towards the common goal. For this, it is necessary to create a traditional and innovative environment of organizing academic activity with spiritual direction in complete and complete synergy. In particular, it is considered a separate infrastructural approach to the use of informational educational tools and methods in improving the social competence of students in the process of higher pedagogical education. The main reason for this is the positive attitude of young people to the media and their quick adaptation. In addition, the world of information quickly attracts students with its attractiveness. Most importantly, teaching and directing students to critically analyze information and use it for noble purposes also provides an opportunity to achieve the development of social competence. However, there is another side of the issue: how do students use the opportunities created? How do such opportunities affect their development? Finding a practical solution to the questions was also chosen as the basis for the organization of the experimental and test work of our research.

It was concluded that it is appropriate to focus on learning the characteristics of social activity in the development of students' social competence. Therefore, comments were made about self-expression and active integration in the levels of socialization presented in the previous paragraph. That is, social competence arises through the manifestation of social activity. Social passivity hurts being sufficiently prepared for professional activity. Therefore, for the student to find answers to the questions he is interested in, it is necessary to have a certain observation and curiosity.

Improving the social competence of students in the process of higher pedagogical education is a task closely related to the content of preparation for professional activity. That is, the social activity of students is not carried out only through the educational tasks within academic subjects, on the contrary, it should be carried out during all kinds of spiritual and educational work of higher education institutions and in the process of voluntary social actions of students. However, the fact that social competence is a component of professional quality that needs to be developed separately is not taken into account either in the content of education, in

the selection of educational forms, or the use of teaching tools. This situation causes a big difference in the ratio of socially active and passive students. To develop social competence, it is possible to justify the need to carry out experimental work on the identification and introduction of pedagogical mechanisms in connection with the following problems:

1) the social passivity of students hurts the full mastery of the essence of the profession. Because passivity in the student weakens the desire for new things and interest in learning. And knowledge, as a phenomenon that should last a lifetime, raises the social status of a person, strengthens his place in society;

2) because social competence is improved based on interpersonal relations, no targeted attention is paid to the development of students' communicative abilities. Special work is required on speech culture, rhetoric, diction, and other professional quality components necessary for the teaching profession. This problem is related to the distance of students from live communication. Students who are used to using information tools and gadgets for various purposes, but spend too much time, do not show enough social skills such as expressive reading skills, beautiful speaking, and clear presentation of thoughts. This is an obstacle to fulfilling the teaching profession. Because the teacher's speech is his professional image. Therefore, the improvement of social competence in students cannot be realized without the development of communicative skills;

3) since "Time management" was selected as a factor with a special place in our research in the structure of social competence, it should be taught to students separately. Therefore, today's specialist needs to understand the importance of time control in every field. There is a need to introduce mechanisms of targeted training of students for the correct use of time in professional activities and its effective use. In practice, there are not enough topics and educational tasks aimed at using time resources during the teaching of specialization and other modules. As a result, students do not develop enough skills to manage the lesson regulations, which are necessary for methodological preparation for professional practice. Making a daily schedule and setting and spending the appropriate time is considered a vital competence. Life and social competencies serve to lead a prosperous and fulfilling lifestyle for a modern person. Therefore, the development of social competencies in students has complex opportunities as it prepares them not only for professional activities but also for a fulfilling life. By itself, the pedagogical process of higher educational institutions should become an environment that ensures the development of the relationship "student-active citizen-responsible person". In it, time and human resources are spent wisely, when pedagogues approach this process with a

motivational orientation as owners of innovative activity.

As a preliminary solution to the listed problems, it is necessary to increase the attention to the implementation of the interaction of educational subjects, and we considered that it is appropriate to organize it in the following directions:

- 1) to fully ensure that the subjects of the block of compulsory subjects are directed to the specialty being prepared and are taught without unproductive repetitions;
- 2) to create an information environment that allows for a more in-depth study of the departments of academic subjects where organizational-methodical, pedagogical-psychological theories, laws, and regulations used in professional activities are described;
- 3) creating and solving professional cases aimed at improving the social competence of students in the process of higher pedagogical education, extensive use of explanatory examples of the studied material;
- 4) implementation of mutual integration of general professional and specialized education by developing a system of complex course projects and works with a clearly expressed professional orientation, united by a single idea.

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